

Stoichiometric versus catalytic action of organocopper compounds in organic transformations

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Have a great historical importance, but still remain highly useful reactions. If not the first organometallic reactions developed they are among the first. In this review, the reactivity of organocopper as a catalyst in organic synthesis is explained. We are elaborately discussed about the stoichiometric versus catalytic action of organocopper compounds in the organic transformation i.e. the change in mechanistic pathway may be observed when the catalysts are directly involved in the reaction with the reacting substrates. Most often used in conjugate addition reactions and couplings with sp^2 carbons, but are also quite useful in epoxide openings. Very recently, the propargylic carbonates were also used to converted to indenenes through a $S_{N2'}$ /Alder-ene cascade triggered by organocopper reagents. S_{N2} and $S_{N2'}$ reactions, and alkyne additions. A deep understanding of the catalytic behavior of organocopper complexes could lead to the design and development of novel reactions that could be accessed by some very selective traditional organometal complex. This critical review describes the stoichiometric reactions of organocopper complexes and discusses their potential mechanism in catalytic reactions.

Keywords: Organocopper chemistry, Gilman cuprates ($R_2CuLi.LiI$), higher order cyanocuprates, lower order cyanocuprates, modified organocopper reagents, substitution/conjugate addition reaction, photoinduced organocopper base organic reaction.

Introduction

Among the variety of transition metal organometallic reagents developed for application to organic synthesis, organocopper reagents are the most widely used and have powerful tools in modern organic synthesis¹. For the reason that of the low polarity of the copper-carbon bond, a unique reactivity profile ranging from conjugate addition and $S_{N2'}$ and S_{N2} -type displacement reactions to carbometalation of alkynes is observed. Furthermore, the organocuprates will undergo anti, $S_{N2'}$ reaction with allylic carboxylates, halides, phosphates, and sulfonates, but syn $S_{N2'}$ reaction with allylic carbamates² and allyloxybenzotriazoles³. This organometallic reagent are tremendous value to the domain of synthetic organic chemistry is hardly open to debate⁴; sooth to say it is rare not to find a copper mediated C-C bond forming transformation in journals that cater to organic chemistry. More recently, a wide range of useful chiral copper catalysts has been developed, which has been reviewed recently⁵. Catalysis is of course only one significant field of application of organometallic chemistry, where assembles a series of elementary reactions to realize product formation while re-forming the necessary reactive intermediates.

The field of catalysis research leverages our understanding of fundamental reactivity at metal centers and challenges us to build up new or ameliorated ways of realizing targeted transformations. During the past decade, this type of selectivity control has been found to be a valuable tool in controlling chemo-, regio-, and stereoselectivity in organocopper catalyzed organic transformations. The aim of this review is to summarize substrate-directed elementary reactions of organocopper reagents, giving importance to synthetically useful transformations.

Organocopper compounds in organometallic chemistry contain carbon to copper chemical bonds. The first organocopper compound, the explosive copper(I) acetylide Cu_2C_2 ($Cu-Ca\equiv C-Cu$), was synthesized by Rudolf Christian Böttger in 1859 by passing acetylene gas through copper(I) chloride solution⁶.

Organocopper compounds in organic chemistry appear most commonly in the form of nucleophilic organocopper(I) reagents, which are used either as stoichiometric reagents or as catalytic species generated in situ from a small amount of a copper(I) complex. Organocopper reagents involve

species containing copper-carbon bonds acting as nucleophiles in the presence of electrophiles in the reaction medium. Organocopper reagents are frequently used in organic transformations as mild, selective nucleophiles for substitution and conjugate addition reactions⁷. In view of the fact that the detection of copper(I) halides catalyze the conjugate addition of Grignard reagents in 1941⁸, and this reagents have emerged as weakly basic, nucleophilic reagents for substitution and addition reactions. The constitution of organocopper compounds depends on their method of preparation and the various kinds of organocopper reagents show different types of reactivity. As a consequence, the extent of reactions involving organocopper reagents is tremendously broad. The nucleophilic organocopper(I) reagents are commonly four types in Fig. 1.

Undoubtedly in organocopper(I) reagents, the cyano ligand, with its π -acidic nature, which enables copper to accept a third negative charged ligand. Although reagents as a "higher order" cyanocuprate do not yet share in all of the benefits offered by time in comparison with their lower-order counterparts, they nicely complement prior art. Moreover, as with species such as RCu , R_2CuLi and $\text{RCu}(\text{CN})\text{Li}$,

they continue to evolve, providing the synthetic community with alternatives for highly selective and efficient means of making key C-C bonds.

Such organocuprates serve as exclusively effective synthetic reagents for grant of hard carbanions such as alkyl, alkenyl, and aryl anions to electrophilic substrates in the form of a variety of reactions such as conjugate addition, carbocupration, alkylation, allylation, alkenylation, acylation, $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ /Alder-ene reaction, $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2'$ to $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ with stereocontrol reaction (Scheme 1)¹³⁻²².

A complete mechanistic picture of representative organocopper(I)-mediated C-C bond forming reactions in Scheme 1 will be illustrated. It should be noted that, while conventional organocopper reagents continue to be important synthetic tools, the expected depletion of rare metal elements has enliven new attention in the use of copper as a universal, base metal for organic synthesis and catalysis²³.

Very recently, spiro Cu^{III} (**3a**) complexes was experimentally observed through a redox transformation of spiro Cu^{I} (**2a**) by treating with reductants or oxidants, respectively

Fig. 1. Types of organocopper.

Scheme 1. Nucleophile C-C bond formation reactions with organocopper reagents.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of organocopper(I) spiro compounds (**2a**) and organocopper(III) spiro compounds (**3a**).

(Scheme 2)²⁴. Organocopper(III) compounds have been proposed as key intermediates in many copper-catalyzed synthetic organic reactions²⁵.

In these reactions, reductive elimination of organocopper(III) compounds is considered as the final step leading to the formation of C-C or C-heteroatom bonds. However, well-defined structures of organocopper(III) compounds remain rather limited to date, which results in the lack of concrete evidence on the reductive elimination of Cu^{III} complexes. Although a few of tetracarbon-coordinated organocuprates(III) have been reported^{26–28}.

Mechanistic aspects of organocopper reactions

Before going into the details, we disclosed the popularity of organocopper complexes as reagents in the mechanisms of nucleophilic organocopper reactions. The field of catalysis research leverages our understanding of fundamental reactivity of organocopper reagents and develops a new way of targeted organic transformations through organocopper-mediated C-C bond formations. Despite of stoichiometric or catalytic processes, the reactions have three elementary steps in widespread, that is, (i) transmetalation between a copper(I) salt and a main-group organometallic reagent to give either a mono- or diorganocuprate(I); (ii) nucleophilic attack of the d-orbital of the copper(I) atom on an electrophile (E⁺) to produce an organocopper(III) intermediate (oxidative addition); and (iii) decomposition (reductive elimination) of the copper(III) intermediate to furnish a product (R-E) and a neutral copper(I) species (Scheme 3).

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Scheme 3. General mechanism of organocopper(I)-mediated C-C bond formation.

In a catalytic reaction, the end species takes part in the next catalytic step. Thus, the transmetalation and the Cu^I/Cu^{III} redox sequence are general key processes in both stoichiometric and catalytic organocopper reactions.

The organocopper complexes used as reagents in organic synthesis have propagated manifold mechanistic investigations of both substitution and conjugate addition reactions. Such types of reaction depends on the nature of the leaving group, the hybridization of the carbon atom take part in the reaction in the substrate and effects of presence of other functional groups in the molecule. Even small differences in solvent, the aggregation state of the reagent and the accompanying salt affect of the composition also have an effect on the reactivity of the reagent. Due to this perplexity, all organocopper reagent, such as low order homocuprates (R₂CuLi)^{63f}, higher order cuprate [R₂Cu(CN)Li]⁶⁴ are added to the solvents like in ether, tetrahydrofuran (THF), and 1,2-dimethoxyethane (DME).

Substitution reactions

The proposed mechanism of nucleophilic substitution of halides or other leaving group by lower-order organocuprates usually involve a direct displacement by R in R₂CuLi in an S_N2' process²⁹; however more recent results suggest that invertive oxidative addition of copper(I) into the carbon-leaving group bond takes place, generating a copper(III) intermediate which then undergoes reductive elimination to generate the coupled product (Scheme 4)³⁰. Both of these mechanisms predict inversion at the electrophilic carbon, which is observed in a number of cases³¹.

Scheme 4. Mechanism of nucleophilic substitution.

Implied in both mechanisms is the stereochemistry at the reacting carbon center, which is predicted to undergo a net inversion. Tosylate³¹ and epoxide³² to give inversion products, but recent evidence shows that such is not the case with all reactive halides^{33,34}. Where the (+)-2-iodooctane lead to racemized products.

X	Outcome at C*
I	Recimization
Br	Inversion
Cl	–
OTs	Inversion

Scheme 5. Reaction of cuprate (R⁻) and 2-halo-octane.

Ashby *et al.*³⁵ have demonstrated that the 6-halo-1-heptenes with X = I, cyclopentane containing products predominant by ratio of 4:1 over straight chain products of substitution. Whereas, X=Br, acyclic containing products predominant over cyclic products of substitution in (Scheme 6).

X	R	%	%
I	Me	18	65
Br	Me	68	0

Scheme 6. Alkyl substitution on straight chain using organocopper reagents.

Alkylations of cyclic and acyclic allylic systems have been scrutinized as to their region- and stereochemical outcomes in reactions with organocuprates. In general, stereochemistry of the products should be *anti*, although it can be reversed i.e. product stereochemistry will be *syn*, depending upon the leaving group^{36,37}, type of substrate and steric factors^{38–41}. More recently studies point to rate determining formation of a σ -allylcopper(III) complex (2), originating from S_N2' attack by organocuprate complex with the olefin (complex 1)^{42,43}. The σ -allylcopper(III) complex undergoes in reductive elimination with retention of configuration would give anti product (4). The σ -allylcopper(III) complex (1) may rapidly isomerizes to a π -allyl species (3) which would give the syn product (11) in Scheme 7.

S_N2 Alkylation reactions

The organocopper reagent Ph₂CuLi undergoes the S_N2 alkylation reactions with secondary alkyl bromide and tosylate give an inversion configuration of the electrophilic carbon center (Figs. 1 and 2)^{44,45}.

Scheme 7. Alkylations of cyclic and acyclic allylic systems.

While the reaction of a secondary alkyl iodide leads to the formation of a racemic product in (Scheme 8) (Fig. 3)⁴⁶.

Scheme 8. S_N2 Alkylation reactions.

The rate of reaction for substitution of alkyl halide and tosylate with R₂CuLi are both first order with respect to the R₂CuLi dimer and the electrophile, whereas, the rate determining step of the reaction is the leaving group displacement from the substrate.

The ring-opening alkylation of an epoxide going through

Scheme 9. Ring opening cyclohexene oxide with Gilman reagent.

Scheme 10. Ring opening of epoxides linked to a primary alcohol with Me₂CuLi.

a similar reaction pathway with the help of Gilman reagent (R₂CuLi) and that has been observed the transdiaxial opening of cyclohexene oxide derivatives (Scheme 9)⁴⁷. The configuration of the electrophilic carbon center is significantly inverted in the TS and this TS leading to the transdiaxial product takes a chair-like conformation, while the diequatorial TS is characterized by a less stable twisted boat conformation.

Naoki and Shinji group⁴⁸, have been described an efficient method for the ring opening of disubstituted epoxides associated to a secondary oxygen group with an organocopper reagent. The 2,3-epoxy alcohols having a substituent at the C-4 position react with Me₂CuLi (Gilman reagent) regioselectively to afford 2-methylated 1,3-diol (Scheme 10, Fig. 1)⁴⁹. The regioselectivity is attributed to hindrance from the C-4 methyl group, rather than a chelation effect by the adjacent hydroxyl group. This is because significant regioselectivity cannot be observed in the absence of the alkyl group at the C4 position (Fig. 2)⁵⁰.

The regioselectivity in the ring opening of epoxides linked to secondary oxygen groups with Gilman reagents, relative configuration of the neighboring secondary alcohol and protection of the alcohol with a TMS or MOM group. Anti-epoxy alcohol tended to react with Me_2CuLi at the C4 position to generate 1,2-diol as a major component. Epoxide linked to a trimethylsilyloxy group displayed selective formation of 1,3-diol. On the other hand, the reactions of syn-epoxy alcohol and the corresponding TMS ether resulted in the selective formation of 1,2-diol in (Scheme 11)⁴⁸.

Scheme 11. Ring opening of epoxides with R_2CuLi .

Thermally stable organocopper(III) spiro compounds **3a** undergo the potential reductive elimination reactions when treated with electrophiles in refluxing condition in presence of THF. Thus, as shown in (Scheme 12)²⁴, **3a** was quenched with 3 (N) HCl at room temperature then it gives us the quantitative isolated yield of *o*-quaterphenyl compound (**4**)⁵¹. Treatment of **3a** with excess I_2 (Iodine), quantitatively produced the diiodo-*o*-quaterphenyl compound (**5**)⁵².

After all, further investigate of the intramolecular $\text{C}(\text{sp}^2)$ - $\text{C}(\text{sp}^2)$ bond-forming reactions, they conducted another

same kind of reaction of **3a** with the reagents 2.0 equiv. of methyl iodide or trimethylsulfonium fluoroborate to produce dimethylo-*o*-quaterphenyl (**6**) in 90% isolated yield⁵¹.

The regio- and stereoselective substitution of allylic electrophiles such as halides and esters with an organo-copper reagent provides an expensive synthetic tool. The reaction is mechanistically much more complicated than the normal substitution reaction of an alkyl halide because the C-C bond formation can take place a priority at the posi-

tion α or γ to the leaving group, and on the *anti* or *syn* face to the leaving group. The regiochemistry in the reactions of organocopper reagents with allylic electrophiles bearing two different types of leaving groups has been studied by Calo and De group. Allylic substitution with organocopper reagents using benzothiazole (**A**) as a substrate afforded homoallylic pivalate (**B**) as a single regioisomer (Scheme 13)⁵³. Hence, the benzothiazole is a much better leaving group than a competing pivaloate one.

Equally, when enoates (**C**) were employed, a high

Scheme 12. Reductive elimination reactions of organocopper(III) spiro compounds **3a**.

Scheme 13. Allylic substitution with organocopper reagents.

Scheme 14. Allylic substitution with high chemo- and regioselectivity toward $S_{N2'}$ reaction.

chemo- and regioselectivity toward $S_{N2'}$ product (D) was observed in (Scheme 14)⁵⁴.

The dialkylcuprate reacts with *cis*-5-methyl-2-cyclohexenyl to produce only an anti-stereoselectivity product but not regioselectively⁵⁵, whereas a heterocuprate $\text{MeCu}(\text{CN})\text{Li}$ undergoes the same reaction in an anti- and γ -selective manner which have been described by Goering *et al.*⁵⁶ (Scheme 15).

Organocopper	α -Adduct (%)	γ -Adduct (%)
$\text{MeCu}(\text{CN})\text{Li}$	4	96
Me_2CuLi	50	50

Scheme 15. Stereo and regioselectivity in allylic substitution.

Enantiomerically enriched allenes can be accessed using diastereomeric carbamates (*R,R*) and (*S,R*)⁵⁷. Propargylic substitution of different substrates with Gilman cuprates gives chiral allenes with 60 to 80% *ee* and in good yields.

Ayako and Hiroshi group⁵⁸ has been described a regio- and (*E*)-stereoselective $S_{N2'}$ ring-opening strategy participating organocopper reagents for converting nonracemic *N*-protected 2,3-*cis*- and 2,3-*trans*-3-alkyl-2-alkenylaziridines to the synthetically important *N*-protected allylamines with good yields. Synthesis of a nonracemic vinylglycine derivative is also diagrammatically represented in (Scheme

Entry	Substrate	R	R'	<i>ee</i> (%)	Yield (%)
1	(<i>R,R</i>)	<i>n</i> Bu	<i>n</i> Bu	80 (<i>S</i>)	76
2	(<i>S,R</i>)	<i>n</i> Bu	<i>n</i> Bu	75 (<i>R</i>)	76
3	(<i>R,R</i>)	Et	Et	60 (<i>S</i>)	73
4	(<i>S,R</i>)	Et	Et	60 (<i>R</i>)	71

Scheme 16. Propargylic substitution of different substrates with Gilman cuprates.

17). There are three different products from the reaction of 2-vinylaziridine **1** with an organocopper reagent could be envisioned. If an organocopper reagent reacts with vinylaziridine **1** by an S_{N2} mechanism, it will produce either **2** or **3**. If the reagent attacks by an $S_{N2'}$ mechanism, it will generate either (*E*)- or (*Z*)-allylamine **4**.

So, the regio- and stereoselectivity of the ring-opening reaction is expected to be controlled by either of steric or electronic factors. Thus, it is difficult to predict whether path A, B, or C is the major reaction pathway in the reaction of 2-alkenylaziridines with organocopper reagents.

The substitution reaction of an acid chloride with an organocuprate reagent, developed in the early 1970s and it is a versatile method for the synthesis of various ketone com-

Scheme 17. Synthesis of a nonracemic vinylglycine derivative.

pounds⁵⁹. The substitution reaction of an acyl electrophile with an organocuprate depends on the nature of the leaving group (Scheme 18)⁶⁰. Because a thiolate anion has a high affinity to a Cu atom, the reaction of a thioester involves insertion of the copper atom into the C-S bond. The acid chloride reacts through an eliminative pathway due to the chloride anion has an electrostatic interaction with the lithium cation.

Scheme 18. Substitution reaction of organocuprate and acyl electrophile

Conjugate addition reactions

The conjugate addition reaction of organocupper reagents to Michael acceptors is a fundamental and among the most useful C-C bond forming reaction organic synthe-

Scheme 19. Conjugate additions of organocuprates.

sis, which may generate a new stereocenter in the position with respect to the acceptor function. The mechanistic presentation of conjugate additions of organocuprates is little bit of complex. Some kind of evidence has been gathered for the existence of an initial complex between the enone and the organocuprate⁶¹. Carbocupration across the carbon-carbon double bond produce a copper enolate in (Scheme 19). However, is conjugate addition of the organocuprate to afford a lithium enolate⁶², consequently reductive elimination and protonation leads to the product⁶³.

The 5-substituted cyclohexenones compounds undergoes in the conjugate addition reaction then both diastereomeric products can be formed selectively with a change of cuprate reagent (Scheme 20)⁶⁴. Thus, the conjugate addition reaction of 5-oxygen-substituted cyclohexenones (1) and (4) with a higher-order cyanocuprate $[(R^1)_2Cu(CN)Li_2]$ give an expected *trans* addition products (3) and (6), respectively. Whereas, the analogous lower-order cyanocuprate $[R^1Cu(CN)Li]$ was treated with 5-oxygen-substituted cyclohexenones (1) and (4), then diastereoselectivity was reversed and the *cis* addition products (2) and (5) was formed in high selectivities which is mechanistically described in Fig. 2.

Scheme 20. Conjugate addition of organocupper reagents to enones compounds.

Fig. 2. conjugate addition on cyclic substrates.

Krause *et al.*³¹ have demonstrated that the reaction of an organocuprate reagent with an extended conjugation carbonyl system may occur at a variety of positions. An exceptional polyenyne system, in which the conjugation is terminated by a C-C triple bond. The remote conjugate addition to polyconjugated carbonyl compounds results in selective or exclusive C-C bond formation at the terminal carbon and hence serves as a practical method for the synthesis of allenes (Scheme 21)⁶⁵.

Scheme 21

Krause proposed a general reaction framework for the remote conjugate addition, where the interaction of a cuprate with the substrate initially generates a β -cuprio(III) enolate (i). This intermediate (i) undergoes sequential migration of the Cu^{III} center via σ/π -allylcopper(III) intermediates (ii) with modest activation energies until the metal atom

reaches the terminal alkyne group and finally take part rapid reductive elimination to yield the corresponding allene product (iii) in Scheme 22.

Reactions of higher-order cyanocuprates with α , β -unsaturated ketones and esters have been studied with regard to such variables as ligand transfer, substrate varieties and solvents^{66,67}. So, Lipshutz and his co-workers have demonstrated that the 3,5,5-trimethylcyclohex-2-enone (A) compound reacts with aryl cuprate $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{Cu}(\text{CN})\text{Li}_2$, successfully form the products of 3,3,5-trimethyl-5-phenylcyclohexanone when $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$ is present in the system (Scheme 22)⁶⁸.

The conjugate addition reaction of cyclopentenones (1) with a higher-order cyanocuprate $[(\text{CH}_2=\text{CH}-)\text{MeCu}(\text{CN})\text{Li}_2]$ to delivered an expected vinylic addition products (2) and other low yield compound (3) have been described by Lipshutz *et al.*⁶⁶ described in (Scheme 24). This pattern holds as well for mixed Gilman cuprates, although the ratio of vinyl to alkyl transfer is somewhat lower.

Reactivity of modified organocopper reagents

In company of the standard Gilman cuprates, a large variety of modified organocuprate reagents have served as useful reagents for C-C bond formation. The modifiers such as usually Lewis acidic or basic additives, are employed for acceleration and/or regio-, chemo-, and stereoselectivity control of the reaction. In this portion, mechanisms behind several representative cases including the effect of BF_3 ,

Scheme 22. General reaction pathway of remote conjugate addition of organocuprate.

Scheme 23. 1,4-Addition of conjugated ketone with higher-order cyanocuprates.

Scheme 24. 1,4-Addition of conjugated ketone with higher-order cyanocuprates.

Me_3SiCl , dummy ligand, and cyano-Gilman cuprate are discussed. An organocopper species generated in a copper-catalyzed reaction of an organometallic reagent (e.g. Mg, Zn, Al) can also be considered as a modified organo-cuprate reagent.

Lewis acid-modified organocopper reagents:

In 1970s Yamamoto and his co-workers⁶⁹ have discovered that the Lewis acidic additive such as BF_3 in conjugate addition of an organocopper reagent to an unsaturated carbonyl compound that increases the reaction rate and changes the selectivity of the addition. A theoretical study of the interaction between $\text{Me}_3\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}$ and BF_3 exposed a strong interaction⁷⁰. The electronegative fluoride ligand coordinates to the Lewis acidic Cu^{III} center, while the Lewis acidic

boron atom interacts with one of the methyl ligands (Scheme 25a).

For the strong interaction the resulting complex have described as $\text{R}_2\text{FCu}^{\text{III}}\cdot\text{BF}_2\text{R}$ rather than $\text{R}_3\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}\cdot\text{BF}_3$. This complex is kinetically unstable toward reductive elimination, because of the poor electron density of the copper atom. In general, BF_3 thermodynamically traps the $\text{R}_3\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}$ species and makes it kinetically labile, which may explain for the accelerated conjugate addition (Scheme 25b).

Me₃SiCl-modified organocopper reagents:

Nakamura/Kuwajima⁷¹, Corey⁷² and Alexakis⁷³ has been independently discovered that the chlorotrimethylsilane (Me_3SiCl) used as a standard reagent for acceleration of conjugate addition reactions. Where the copper-catalyzed conjugate additions of zinc homoenolates was first reported on that time in Scheme 26⁷¹.

Me_3SiCl was also used to the chemoselectivity of organocuprate reactions. The reaction between allyl phosphate and an enone in presence of standard copper reagent is dominated by the allylic substitution, whereas the addition of Me_3SiCl completely alters the chemoselectivity (Scheme 27)⁷⁴.

Dummy ligand effect:

One of the two R groups of a homocuprate reagent R_2CuLi can transfer to the electrophilic substrate and another one is lost as an unreactive RCu species. When the R group is precious then this inherent reactivity is create a

Scheme 25. Complexation of $\text{R}_3\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}$ species with BF_3 by conjugate addition.

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Scheme 26. Copper-catalyzed conjugate additions of zinc homoenolates.

Scheme 27. Me₃SiCl-assisted conjugated addition of organocopper to cyclohexene.

problem. To solve this problem, a mixed organocuprate R(X)CuLi was first introduced by Corey in 1972 in which the X group acts as a nontransferable dummy ligand (X = alkynyl; Scheme 28)⁷⁵.

Scheme 28. Ligand transfer in conjugate addition of mixed organocuprate.

Further studies, synthetically useful mixed organocuprates containing a series of dummy ligands including, -cyano, -alkynyl, -phenylthio, -alkoxy, -dialkylamino, -phosphido, and -trimethylsilylmethyl groups have been developed. The dummy ligand approach also led to the invention of chiral mixed organocuprates, which serve as reagents for enantioselective conjugate addition⁷⁶.

The reactivity of heterocuprates in allylic substitution and conjugate addition reactions exposed numerous factors that control transferability of ligands on cuprates⁷⁷. The reductive elimination of Me(X)Cu(η^3 -allyl) demonstrated that the Me-allyl bond formation is preferred to X-allyl bond formation for the common dummy ligands, that is, X = C₂H₂, CN, SiMe, and CH₂SiMe₃ analyzed in Scheme 29.

Scheme 29. Reductive elimination of Me(X)Cu(η^3 -allyl).

Organocopper reagents easily react with heterocyclic propargyl mesylates at low temperature to give *N*-fused heterocycles. The copper reagent plays a “double duty” in this cascade transformation, which proceeds via an S_N2' substitution followed by a subsequent cycloisomerization step. Dmitri, Surendra Babu group²⁴, have been reported that the organocopper-mediated coupling as well as cyclization in cascade reaction of propargyl mesylates derivatives (**A**) toward *N*-fused heterocyclic frameworks (**B**) in Scheme 30.

Scheme 30. Synthesis of *N*-fused heterocyclic frameworks.

Dmitri groups propose the following mechanism for the substitution/cycloisomerization cascade of propargyl mesylates (**A**) with copper reagents into *N*-fused heterocycles (**B**) (Scheme 31)⁷⁸. At first, S_N2' substitution of mesylate in (**A**) leads to allene (**D**), which undergoes intramolecular nucleophilic attack of pyridyl nitrogen at the Cu-activated double bond of allene, produces cyclic intermediate (**E**). Finally it can transform into product (**B**) via the deprotonation-protonation pathways.

Extent and abridgements

Reactions of organocopper compounds can be divided into stoichiometric variants and catalytic. Even though organocopper compounds have primarily been used in stoichiometric amounts for organic synthesis, catalytic methods are useful for enantioselective reactions and require less preparation than stoichiometric methods. In this portion we have described both stoichiometric and catalytic reactions of organocopper complexes, with a particular

Scheme 31. Proposed mechanism for cascade cyclization using lower order cyanocuprates reagents.

concentration on the nucleophilic substitution and conjugate addition reactions.

Stoichiometric reactions of organocopper compounds

Kleijn and Elsevier group⁷⁹ has been described that Propargyl methanesulfonates are useful substrates for the synthesis of allenes from stoichiometric organocopper complexes in Scheme 32. In this case, the complexes were generated *in situ* through the combination of a Grignard reagent, copper(I) bromide, and lithium bromide. Organo-

Scheme 32. Synthesis of α and β -allenic alcohols via organocopper(I) induced 1,3-substitution in propargylic methanesulfonates.

Scheme 33. Highly stereoselective synthesis of trisubstituted olefins via addition of alkylcopper complexes to acetylenes.

Scheme 34. Li_2CuCl_4 used as a superior catalyst in cross-coupling reaction.

copper complexes very frequently need Lewis acid activation in order to react efficiently and on the other hand magnesium bromide generated *in situ* serves as an activating Lewis acid in this case.

Marfat *et al.*⁸⁰ have demonstrated that the compound (A) is employed in reactions with Grignard reagents, the resulting alkylcopper complexes undergo addition to terminal acetylenes to give high yields of products derived from the disubstituted alkenylcopper intermediates (B). This Alkenylcopper complexes readily undergo conjugate addition to a number of α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds to give the desired trisubstituted olefins (C) in Scheme 33.

Catalytic reactions of organocopper compounds

Nunomoto and Yamashita group⁸¹ have been focused on the cross-coupling reaction of 1,3-butadien-2-ylmagnesium chloride with alkyl or aryl halides by lithium chloride-cupric chloride (Li_2CuCl_4), a superior catalyst. The use of Li_2CuCl_4 rather than simple copper(I) halide salts (CuX) improves yields of these coupling reactions substantially in Scheme 34.

Photoinduced organocopper based organic reactions

Alkylation of terminal alkynes and their derivatives is an important approach to the synthesis of internal alkynes. In recent time, various type of methods are accessible for the alkylation of prefunctionalized alkyne substrates, such as haloalkynes⁸², metal acetylides⁸³, alkynylbenziodoxolones⁸⁴ and alkynyl sulfones⁸⁵. A good number of catalytic methods⁸⁶ for the alkylation of terminal alkynes rely on in situ formation of copper acetylides, which acts as a key of catalytic intermediates (Scheme 35). They are easily formed from terminal alkynes in the presence of a weak base and a copper salt⁸⁷. However, the low nucleophilicity of copper acetylides makes their alkylation challenging⁸⁷. Direct alkylation can only be achieved using strong electrophiles, such as primary alkyl triflates⁸⁸, activated α - and β -haloamides⁸⁹, oxocarbenium ions⁹⁰ and iminium ions (Scheme 35a)⁹¹. Alternatively, the alkylation of copper acetylides can be accomplished using Sonogashira reaction⁹², which requires an additional transition metal catalyst (Scheme 35b).

Hazra and Lalic group⁹³, have been developed a light-promoted, coppercatalyzed coupling of terminal alkynes and alkyl halides as electrophiles in (Scheme 35c). The alkylation is promoted by using blue light (~ 450 nm) and proceeds at room temperature in the absence of any additional metal catalysts. The use of a various types of terpyridine ligand is essential for the success of the reaction and is shown to prevent photoinduced coppercatalyzed polymerization of the starting materials.

Blue light and the copper catalyst were both necessary for the alkylation of terminal alkynes. The ligand **L1** (4,4',4''-tri *tert*-butyl-2,2':6',2''-terpyridine) was determined to be essential to the success of the reaction in (Scheme 36). In the absence of the ligand, Hazra and his co-worker obtained very low yield of the desired product, with the major product being polymerization of the starting material.

After some short of investigations of the photophysical properties of copper acetylides, Hazra and his co-warker suggest that the similar approach can be used to achieve photoinduced, copper-catalyzed alkylation of terminal alkynes according to the mechanism outlined in Scheme 37.

(a) Reactions with strong electrophiles

E^+ = Iminium ions, oxonium ions, haloamides, alkyl triflates

(b) Sonogashira Coupling

R^1-X = Primary and Secondary alkyl halides

(c) Hazra and Lalic group work

R^1-X = Primary, Secondary and bridgehead tertiary alkyl halides

Scheme 35. Copper-catalyzed alkylation of terminal alkynes.

Scheme 36. Hazra and his co-worker established photoinduced Cu-catalysed coupling reaction.

Scheme 37. Plausible mechanism of photoinduced alkylation.

Conclusion

The organocopper chemistry described above is an already mature field that has found many practical applications in substitution and conjugate addition reaction of various organic substrates. The selectivity of reactions involving organocopper reagents can be controlled efficiently upon use of attractive substrate-reagent interactions. These substrate-directed reactions specify the regio- and stereoselectivity, whereas the nondirected counterparts indicate the steric and electronic factors are dominant. The nucleophilic organocopper(I) reagents and catalysts have been used as the most synthetically useful and versatile species in organic synthesis. The organocopper(I)-mediated C-C bond forming reactions usually engage in three elementary steps: (i) transmetalation with main-group organometallics; (ii) oxidative addition of an electrophile to Cu^{I} and (iii) reductive elimination of the resulting organocopper(III) species. The ability of organocuprates to form a variety of entirety structures with Lewis acids and Lewis bases is also critical for the reaction to be successful. Lewis acidic metal atoms not only activate the electrophile and thereby facilitate the oxidative addition, but also may bind to the organocopper(III) intermediate to promote the reductive elimination. It is now established beyond any hesitation that the nucleophilic organocopper mechanism is the one operating in a majority of the reactions. We hope that the fundamental mechanistic frameworks discussed in this review will help understanding of new reactivity of organocopper reactions and designing of new reactions mediated or catalyzed by organocopper. On the other application sites is a light-induced, copper catalyzed coupling of terminal alkynes with unactivated primary, secondary, and tertiary alkyl iodides. The reaction has a wide substrate scope and is well-suited with esters, nitriles, alcohols, amides, epoxides, aryl

halides, and ethers. The alkylation reaction in the presence of terpyridine ligand proceeds through a direct coupling between copper acetylide and an unactivated alkyl iodide, most likely with the taking part of free-radical intermediates. Last but not least, the rebirth of high-order organocopper chemistry introduced first about few years ago, which was boosted by new demanding practical applications of synthetic organic chemistry.

References

- (a) G. H. Posner, *Org. React.*, 1972, **19**, 1; (b) B. H. Lipshutz and S. Sengupta, *Org. React.*, 1992, **41**, 135.
- S. E. Denmark and L. K. Marble, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1990, **55**, 1984.
- S. Valverde, M. Bernabé, S. Garcia-Ochoa and A. M. Gómez, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1990, **55**, 2294.
- G. A. Posner, "An Introduction to Synthesis Using Organocopper Reagents", Wiley, New York, 1980.
- (a) S. Woodward, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2005, **44**, 5560; (b) A. Alexakis, C. Malan, L. Lea, K. Tissot-Croset, D. Polet and C. Falciola, *Chimia*, 2006, **60**, 124.
- R. C. Bottger, *Annalen.*, 1859, **109**, 351 (doi:10.1002/jlac.18591090318).
- B. H. Lipshutz and S. Sengupta, *Org. React.*, 1992, **41**, 135.
- M. S. Kharasch and P. O. Tawney, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 2308.
- V. K. Kansal and R. J. K. Taylor, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1984, 703.
- G. H. Posner, *Org. React.*, 1975, **22**, 253.
- B. H. Lipshutz and S. Sengupta, *Org. React.*, 1992, **41**, 135.
- B. H. Lipshutz, R. S. Wilhelm and D. M. Floyd, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **103**, 7672.
- J. F. Normant, *Synthesis*, 1972, 63.
- (a) G. H. Posner, *Org. React.*, 1972, **19**, 1; (b) G. H. Posner, *Org. React.*, 1975, **22**, 253.
- Y. Yamamoto, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1986, **25**, 947.
- E. Nakamura, *Synlett*, 1991, 539.
- B. H. Lipshutz and S. Sengupta, *Org. React.*, 1992, **41**, 135.
- N. Krause and A. Gerold, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1997, **36**, 186.
- "Modern Organocopper Chemistry", ed. N. Krause, Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, 2002.
- "The Chemistry of Organocopper Compounds: Part 1 and Part 2", eds. Z. Rappoport and I. Marek, Wiley, Chichester, 2009.
- T. Arif, C. Borie, M. Jean, N. Vanthuynne, M. P. Bertrand, D. Siri and M. Nechab, *Org. Chem. Front.*, 2018, **5**, 769.
- (a) B. M. Trost and L. Debie, *Chem. Sci.*, 2016, **7**, 4985; (b) J. Robertson and S. Naud, *Org. Lett.*, 2008, **10**, 5445; (c) Y. Wang and J. M. Ready, *Org. Lett.*, 2012, **14**, 2308; (d) P. J. Parsons, J. Board, D. Faggiani, P. B. Hitchcock, L. Preece and A. J. Waters, *Tetrahedron*, 2008, **66**, 6526; (e) M. R.

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- Uehling, S. T. Mariotti and G. Lalic, *Org. Lett.*, 2012, **14**, 362; (f) H. Li, D. Müller, L. Guenee and A. Alexakis, *Org. Lett.*, 2012, **14**, 5880; (g) H. Ohmiya, U. Yokobori, Y. Makida and M. Sawamura, *Org. Lett.*, 2011, **13**, 6312; (h) M. Yang, N. Yokokawa, H. Ohmiya and M. Sawamura, *Org. Lett.*, 2012, **14**, 816; (i) R. K. Neff and D. E. Frantz, *ACS Catal.*, 2014, **4**, 519.
23. E. Nakamura and K. Sato, *Nat. Mater.*, 2011, **10**, 158.
 24. L. Liu, M. Zhu, H. T. Yu, W. X. Zhang and Z. Xi, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2017, **139**, 13688.
 25. (a) E. Sperotto, G. P. M. van Klink, G. van Koten and J. G. de Vries, *Dalton Trans.*, 2010, **39**, 10338; (b) A. E. Wendlandt, A. M. Suess and S. Stahl, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2011, **50**, 11062; (c) A. J. Hickman and M. S. Sanford, *Nature*, 2012, **484**, 177; (d) N. Yoshikai and E. Nakamura, *Chem. Rev.*, 2012, **112**, 2339; (e) G. van Koten, *Organometallics*, 2012, **31**, 7634.
 26. (a) D. Naumann, T. Roy, K.-F. Tebbe and W. Crump, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed. Engl.*, 1993, **32**, 1482; (c) J. A. Schlueter, U. Geiser, J. M. Williams, H. H. Wang, W.-K. Kwok, J. A. Fendrich, K. D. Carlson, C. A. Achenbach, J. D. Dudek, D. Naumann, T. Roy, J. E. Schirber and W. R. Bayless, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1994, 1599; (d) R. Eujen, B. Hoge and D. J. Brauer, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1996, **519**, 7; (e) A. M. Romine, N. Nebra, A. I. Konovalov, E. Martin, J. Benet-Buchholz and V. V. Grushin, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2015, **54**, 2745.
 27. (a) R. M. Wing, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **90**, 4828; (b) A. Varadarajan, S. E. Johnson, F. A. Gomez, S. Chakrabarti, C. B. Knobler and M. F. Hawthorne, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **114**, 9003; (c) D. E. Harwell, J. McMillan, C. B. Knobler and M. F. Hawthorne, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1997, **36**, 5951.
 28. G. García-López, V. Yañez-Rodríguez, L. Rocas, S. Garcia-Granda, A. Martínez, A. Guevara-García, G. R. Castro, F. Jiménez-Villacorta, M. J. Iglesias and F. L. Ortiz, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2010, **132**, 10665.
 29. M. Tamura and J. K. Kochi, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1972, **42**, 205.
 30. E. J. Corey and N. W. Boaz, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1984, **25**, 3059.
 31. C. R. Johnson and G. A. Dutra, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **95**, 7777.
 32. J. Fried, C. H. Lin, J. C. Sih, P. Dalven and G. F. Cooper, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 4342.
 33. B. H. Lipshutz and R. S. Wilhelm, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **104**, 4696.
 34. E. Hebert, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1982, **23**, 415.
 35. E. C. Ashby and D. Coleman, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1987, **52**, 4554.
 36. C. Gallina and P. G. Ciattini, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **101**, 1035.
 37. H. L. Goering and C. C. Tseng, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1985, **50**, 1597.
 38. E. J. Corey and J. Mann, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **95**, 6832.
 39. A. Kreft, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1977, 1035.
 40. C. B. Chapleo, M. A. W. Finch, T. V. Lee and S. M. Roberts, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1979, 676.
 41. C. B. Chapleo, M. A. W. Finch, T. V. Lee, G. T. Roberts, Woolley, R. F. Newton and D. W. Seibly, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans.*, 1980, **1**, 1847.
 42. H. L. Goering, S. S. Kanter and E. P. Seitz, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1985, **50**, 5495.
 43. J. Levisalles, M. Rudler-Chauvin and H. Rudler, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1977, **136**, 103.
 44. G. M. Whitesides, W. F. Fischer (Jr.), J. San Filippo (Jr.), R. W. Bashe and H. O. House, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 4871.
 45. C. R. Johnson and G. A. Dutra, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **95**, 7783.
 46. B. H. Lipshutz and R. S. Wilhelm, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **104**, 4696.
 47. B. Rickborn, B. M. Trost, I. Fleming, (Eds.), Pergamon Press, Elmsford, New York, 1991, **3**, 733.
 48. N. Terayama, S. Ushijima, E. Yasui, M. Miyashita and S. Nagumo, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2014, **55**, 6515.
 49. M. R. Johnson, T. Nakata and Y. Kishi, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1979, **20**, 4343.
 50. L. Kong, Z. Zhuang, Q. Chen, H. Deng, Z. Tang, X. Jia, Y. Li and H. Zhai, *Tetrahedron Asymm.*, 2007, **18**, 451.
 51. J. He, J. L. Crase, S. H. Wadumethrige, K. Thakur, L. Dai, S. Zou, R. Rathore and C. S. Hartley, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2010, **132**, 13848; (b) Y. Zhang, J. Han and Z.-J. Liu, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2016, **81**, 1317.
 52. G. Wittig and G. Klar, *Justus Liebigs Ann. Chem.*, 1967, **704**, 91.
 53. V. Calo', C. De Nitti, L. Lopez and A. Scilimati, *Tetrahedron*, 1992, **48**, 6051.
 54. V. Calo', L. Lopez and G. Pesce, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1986, 1252.
 55. (a) H. L. Goering and V. D. Singleton, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **98**, 7854; (b) H. L. Goering and V. D. Singleton, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1983, **48**, 1531.
 56. H. L. Goering and S. S. Kantner, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1984, **49**, 422.
 57. W. H. Pirkle and C. W. Boeder, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1978, **43**, 1950.
 58. A. Toda, H. Aoyama, N. Mimura, H. Ohno, N. Fujii and Ibuka, Toshiro., *J. Org. Chem.*, 1998, **63**, 7053.
 59. G. H. Posne and C. E. Whitten, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1970, 4647.
 60. N. Yoshikai, R. Iida and E. Nakamura, *Adv. Synth. Catal.*, 2008, **350**, 1063.
 61. P. Four, H. Riviere and P. W. Tang, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1977, 3879.
 62. S. R. Krauss and S. G. Smith, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1981,

- 103, 141.
63. S. Woodward, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2000, **29**, 393.
64. (a) S. Hikichi, G. Hareau and F. Sato, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1997, **38**, 8299; (b) G. Hareau- Vittini, S. Hikichi and F. Sato, *Angew. Chem.*, 1998, **110**, 2221; (c) G. Hareau-Vittini, S. Hikichi and F. Sato, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 1998, **37**, 2099; (d) G. Hareau, M. Koiwa, T. Hanazawa and F. Sato, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1999, **40**, 7493; (e) G. Hareau, M. Koiwa, S. Hikichi and F. Sato, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **121**, 3640.
65. N. Krause and A. Hoffmann-Röder, in: "Modern Organocopper Chemistry", eds. N. Krause, Wiley-VCH, Weinheim, 2001, pp. 145-166. (b) N. Krause and S. Thorand, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1999, **296**, 1; (c) N. Krause, *Chem. Ber.*, 1990, **123**, 2173; (d) N. Krause, *Chem. Ber.*, 1991, **124**, 2633; (e) G. Handke, N. Krause, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1993, **34**, 6037; (f) B. H. Lipshutz, J. A. Kozlowski and C. M. Breneman, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1985, **107**, 3197; (g) A. Haubrich, M. Vanklaveren, G. Vankoten, G. Handke and N. Krause, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1993, **58**, 5849.
66. B. H. Lipshutz, R.S. Wilhelm and J. A. Kozlowski, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1984, **49**, 3938.
67. B. H. Lipshutz, R. S. Wilhelm and J. A. Kozlowski, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1982, **23**, 3755.
68. B. H. Lipshutz, D. A. Parker, J. A. Kozlowski and S. L. Nuyen, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1984, **25**, 5959.
69. (a) K. Maruyama and Y. Yamamoto, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **99**, 8068; (b) Y. Yamamoto, S. Yamamoto, H. Yatagai and K. Maruyama, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **102**, 2318; (c) Y. Yamamoto and K. Maruyama, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **100**, 3240.
70. E. Nakamura, M. Yamanaka and S. Mori, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **122**, 1826.
71. E. Nakamura and I. Kuwajima, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **106**, 3368.
72. (a) E. J. Corey and N. W. Boaz, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1985, **26**, 6015; (b) E. J. Corey and N. W. Boaz, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1985, **26**, 6019.
73. A. Alexakis, J. Berlan and Y. Besace, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1986, **27**, 1047.
74. M. Arai, B. H. Lipshutz and E. Nakamura, *Tetrahedron*, 1992, **48**, 5709.
75. E. J. Corey and D. J. Beames, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 7210.
76. B. E. Rossiter and N. M. Swingle, *Chem. Rev.* 1992, **92**, 771.
77. (a) E. Nakamura and M. Yamanaka, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **121**, 8941; (b) M. Yamanaka and E. Nakamura, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **127**, 4697.
78. D. Chernyak, S. B. Gadamssetty and V. Gevorgyan, *Org. Lett.*, 2008, **10**, 2307.
79. H. Kleijn, C. J. Elsevier, H. Westmijze, J. Meijer and P. Vermeer, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1979, **33**, 3101.
80. A. Marfat, P. R. McGuirk and P. Helquist, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1979, **44**, 3888.
81. S. Nunomoto, Y. Kawakami and Y. Yamashita, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1983, **48**, 1912.
82. (a) G. Cahiez, O. Gager and J. Buendia, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2010, **49**, 1278; (b) Y. Shen, B. Huang, J. Zheng, C. Lin, Y. Liu and S. Cui, *Org. Lett.*, 2017, **19**, 1744; (c) T. Thaler, L.-N. Guo, P. Mayer and P. Knochel, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2011, **50**, 2174; (d) L. Huang, A. M. Olivares and D. J. Weix, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2017, **56**, 11901.
83. (a) T. Hatakeyama, Y. Okada, Y. Yoshimoto and M. Nakamura, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2011, **50**, 10973; (b) H. Ohmiya, H. Yorimitsu and K. Oshima, *Org. Lett.*, 2006, **8**, 3093; (c) O. Vechorkin, A. Godinat, R. Scopelliti and X. Hu, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2011, **50**, 11777; (d) C. W. Cheung, P. Ren and X. Hu, *Org. Lett.*, 2014, **16**, 2566; (e) J. M. Smith, T. Qin, R. R. Merchant, J. T. Edwards, L. R. Malins, Z. Liu, G. Che, Z. Shen, S. A. Shaw, M. D. Eastgate and P. S. Baran, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2017, **56**, 11906.
84. (a) F. Le Vaillant, T. Courant and J. Waser, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2015, **54**, 11200; (b) X. Liu, Z. Wang, X. Cheng and C. Li, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **134**, 14330; (c) H. Huang, G. Zhang, L. Gong, S. Zhang and Y. Chen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2014, **136**, 2280; (d) C. Yang, J.-D. Yang, Y.-H. Li, X. Li and J.-P. Cheng, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2016, **81**, 12357.
85. J. Yang, J. Zhang, L. Qi, C. Hu and Y. Chen, *Chem. Commun.*, 2015, **51**, 5275.
86. W. Liu, L. Li and C.-J. Li, *Nature Commun.*, 2015, **6**, 6526.
87. G. Evano, K. Jouvin, C. Theunissen, C. Guissart, A. Laouiti, C. Tresse, J. Heimbürger, Y. Bouhoute, R. Veillard, M. Lecomte, A. Nitelet, S. Schweizer, N. Blanchard, C. Alayrac and A. C. Gaumont, *Chem. Commun.*, 2014, **50**, 10008.
88. L. Jin, W. Hao, J. Xu, N. Sun, B. Hu, Z. Shen, W. Mo and X. Hu, *Chem. Commun.*, 2017, **53**, 4124.
89. (a) F.-X. Luo, X. Xu, D. Wang, Z.-C. Cao, Y.-F. Zhang, Z.-J. Shi, *Org. Lett.*, 2016, **18**, 2040; (b) Y. Yamane, N. Miwa and T. Nishikata, *ACS Catalysis*, 2017, **7**, 6872.
90. (a) P. Maity, H. D. Srinivas and M. P. Watson, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2011, **133**, 17142; (b) H. D. Srinivas, P. Maity, G. P. A. Yap and M. P. Watson, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2015, **80**, 4003; (c) S. Dasgupta, T. Rivas and M. P. Watson, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2015, **54**, 14154.
91. (a) H.-P. Bi, L. Zhao, Y.-M. Liang and C.-J. Li, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2009, **48**, 792; (b) C. Zhang and D. Seidel, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2010, **132**, 1798; (c) H. Zhang, P. Zhang, M. Jiang, H. Yang and H. Fu, *Org. Lett.*, 2017, **19**, 1016.
92. (a) R. Chinchilla and C. Nájera, *Chem. Rev.*, 2007, **107**, 874; (b) R. Chinchilla and C. Najera, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2011, **40**, 5084.
93. A. Hazra, M. T. Lee, J. F. Chiu and G. Lalic, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2018, **57**, 5492 (DOI: 10.1002/anie.201801085).